

COST CA20108 INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

FAIRNESS

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

ADVANCING FAIR DATA AND STANDARDIZATION IN MICROMETEOROLOGICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL NETWORKS

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

This publication is based upon work from COST Action FAIR Network of micrometeorological measurements supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

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Networking and Communication

Forest Micrometeorology Networks: A Strategic Framework for Multidisciplinary Collaboration

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Establishing collaborative networks for forest micrometeorology is essential for understanding forest-atmosphere interactions, improving climate resilience, and supporting sustainable forest management. This study presents a strategic framework for fostering interdisciplinary partnerships among meteorologists, ecologists, foresters, climate scientists, and policymakers. The approach involves defining clear research objectives, such as assessing bioclimatic comfort, monitoring forest microclimates, and analysing the impacts of climate change on forest ecosystems. Engaging key stakeholders—including research institutions, forestry agencies, NGOs, and local communities—ensures that scientific insights translate into practical applications.

A core component of this strategy is developing open-access data-sharing platforms that integrate GIS-based repositories and existing networks like FLUXNET and Copernicus Climate Data Store. Standardized data collection methodologies and the deployment of real-time monitoring networks (e.g., flux towers, IoT-based weather stations) enhance the accuracy of micrometeorological assessments. Furthermore, interdisciplinary collaboration through joint research projects, AI-driven data analytics, and remote sensing applications strengthens data-driven forest management practices.

Securing funding from international programs such as Horizon Europe, FAO, and UNEP is critical for sustaining long-term research efforts. Finally, integrating micrometeorological findings into policy frameworks facilitates adaptive forest management, enhances biodiversity conservation, and supports climate-responsive land-use planning. This holistic approach ensures that forest micrometeorology plays a pivotal role in shaping sustainable forestry and climate adaptation strategies.

Keywords: Forest micrometeorology, Climate, FLUXNET, Copernicus

Advancing urban climate monitoring: Fostering multidisciplinary collaboration among institutions in Southeast Europe over the last decade

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Over the past decade, urban climate monitoring in Southeast Europe has undergone significant advancements, driven by the increasing recognition of climate change impacts on urban environments. A notable example is the Novi Sad Urban Climate Lab (NSUCL), which has established itself as a pioneering institution in the region, focusing on innovative research and practical solutions for urban climate challenges. Through collaborative efforts among universities and local decision-makers, the NSUCL has developed comprehensive monitoring frameworks that integrate various scientific disciplines, including meteorology, environmental science, and urban design.

The establishment of regional networks and mobile monitoring initiatives has fostered a collaborative approach to addressing urban climate challenges. Some common research results reveal that strategically placing additional trees, considering various crown shapes, can lower outdoor thermal comfort values in Novi Sad at specific locations by up to 6.11°C (UTCI), underscoring the critical importance of selecting optimal tree placements to maximize thermal comfort on hot summer days. Also, mobile observations have shown temperature differences between grey and green areas from 1.5°C (Trebinje) to 4.8°C (Belgrade). Therefore, these networks and datasets have also played a crucial role in securing funding for research projects, enabling the implementation of pilot programs aimed at mitigating climate impacts in urban settings.

Despite these advancements, challenges remain, including the need for standardized data collection methods and increased investment in infrastructure. Future efforts should focus on sustaining interdisciplinary collaboration, enhancing data accessibility, and integrating climate considerations into urban development policies.

Keywords: Urban climate monitoring, multidisciplinary, thermal comfort, mobile observations

Acknowledgment: This research was conducted within the European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) Grant CA20108 (FAIRNESS project).

A rural tall-mast eddy covariance dataset for multi-purpose use

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Despite the development of remote sensing techniques, the *in-situ* measurements of planetary boundary layer (PBL) stratification still provide most accurate information on surface fluxes of gases and aerosol particles, and dispersion conditions for air pollutants from anthropogenic sources. The measurements in the tallest masts represent a remarkable part of PBL height, or even pierce through the entire PBL, if it is thin enough, usually in the case of stable stratification.

In 2015 – 2020 the Valgjärve TV mast in South-Eastern Estonia was used for eddy covariance measurements. The mast (geographical coordinates: 58°05'50"N, 26°40'41"E) is located in a hilly rural mosaic landscape of forest and open fields with small lakes. The foot of the mast is on the top of a local height, 187 m above sea level. The construction is 347 meters tall, of which 200 meters was used for measurements. 3D sonic anemometers Metek Class A were installed at heights of 30, 50, 110, and 200 meters above the underlying surface. The temperature and humidity sensors of Rotronic HygroClip HC2-S3 were installed at the same heights. A 4-component radiometer Kipp & Zonen NCR4 was installed at the highest level, 200 m.

The raw data consists of wind components and temperature measured at 40 Hz frequency. The condensed data set includes one-second averages, dispersions, and covariances of wind components and sonic temperature. Apart from the initial purpose of quantifying the kinetic energy and momentum fluxes in PBL for climate research purposes, the data are used in the (weather forecast model) HIRLAM validation system, managed by the Finnish Meteorological Institute. The condensed data set is uploaded to the Micromet KSP data repository of FAIRNESS.

Keywords: Eddy covariance, tall-mast measurements, planetary boundary layer, FAIR data

Acknowledgment: This data was collected in the framework of the project Estonian Environmental Observatory, funded by Estonian Research Council. Measurements were carried out in cooperation with Levira AS, the owner of Valgjärve TV mast.

Application of WRF - ARW model at a small grid size of 1×1 km for forecasting micro weather parameters at Volos city, Greece

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In recent years, there have been significant advancements in computer science along with new data capabilities. According to that, the open-source, well-established Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model has the opportunity of a worldwide evolution. This study explores the application of the WRF model using the Advanced Research WRF (ARW) core at a high spatial resolution of 1×1 km. The primary objective is to assess the model's performance in predicting localized atmospheric conditions, including temperature, wind speed, humidity, and precipitation, which are essential parameters for various meteorological and urban applications. The study utilizes high-resolution topographical data to enhance model accuracy to better capture the region's complex orography and coastal influence, which is an important characteristic for the city of Volos. The model simulations are evaluated against observational data from local meteorological stations to validate their performance. The preliminary results indicate that the proposed high-resolution WRF-ARW setup presents fine-scale atmospheric dynamics and may visualize temperature variations within the urban environment, as well as sea breeze circulations, and/or convection. The 1×1 km grid size enhances the model's ability to resolve microclimatic features, which are often not included in coarser simulations. However, challenges such as computational demand and sensitivity to physical parameterization schemes remain critical and require further consideration.

Keywords: WRF-ARW, micro-weather forecasting, high-resolution modeling, Volos, Greece, urban meteorology.

Gap Filling: Building a MetaLearner for Python's Interpolation Functions

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Missingness, the degree to which data are missing from a dataset, generally takes one of 3 forms: Missing at Random (MAR); Missing Completely at Random (MCAR); and Missing Not at Random (MNAR). The MAR scenario refers to data missing randomly in set situations, for example, clear sky rarely has missing data, whereas cloudy skies can often contain missing data. If data is randomly missing for all cases, for example, for clear sky or any type of cloud cover, this implies the MCAR scenario. If neither MAR nor MCAR is present, then missing data is regarded as MNAR. For example, data is missing for reasons unknown, perhaps with no discernible pattern.

Python offers a range of interpolation functions, potentially providing a systematic and standardised mechanism for filling gaps. One class of imputation algorithm is *univariate*, which imputes using non-missing values *in that feature only*. The second class, *multivariate* imputation, uses all available features to impute the missing values. This provides both efficient and accurate methods of interpolation for scientists with the added benefit of a standard methodology for filling gaps in their data.

Concentrating on 1-D interpolation alone, there are a range of different functions, each of which will deliver different levels of accuracy. Assuming that each function is highly accurate or optimal, this means that certain characteristics of the dataset require a different interpolation method. The challenge for non-IT scientists such as climate researchers, is how to determine which interpolation function best suits their data. In this work, we build a meta-learner for 4 of Python's 1-D interpolation functions (Nearest, Linear, Splines and Akima) using 50,000 time series data, by testing the predictive performance of each interpolation function. This enables the building of a classifier which can be used to recommend the best performing function for each target dataset.

Keywords: Gap filling, missing data, Python interpolation, meta-learning, time series imputation

Improving satellite-based actual evapotranspiration estimations using data from local weather stations

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Evapotranspiration (ET) is critical for water resource management, agricultural planning, and understanding land-atmosphere interactions. This study focused on improving the accuracy and applicability of the Sentinel for Evapotranspiration (Sen-ET) plugin for ET estimation in a different range of field crops relevant to Israel. The goals were primarily to validate the Sen-ET method, using eddy covariance (EC) measurements, to test the hypothesis that data from local weather stations can improve estimates, and to determine how the distance of the weather station from the field affects the accuracy of the model's estimates. The research was conducted across eight test sites featuring spring wheat, potato, cotton, and tomato fields. High-resolution Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 imagery, along with ERA-5 and local meteorological data, were used to estimate ET via the Two Source Energy Balance model. Results showed that incorporating local weather station data significantly improved accuracy, with RMSE reductions observed at most sites. For example, at a wheat site, the RMSE dropped from 0.60 mm day⁻¹ to 0.14 mm day⁻¹. However, at a tomato site, using data from a distant weather station (7 km) increased RMSE by 0.01 mm day⁻¹, whereas a closer station (1.17 km) reduced it by 0.34 mm day⁻¹. Subsequently, occurrences of large differences between weather data sources were explored to evaluate the effect on ET estimation, and solar radiation emerged as the most significant contributor to improving the model's predictions. These findings offer a way forward for developing operational models to support sustainable irrigation management. FAIR Data and Standardization in micrometeorological and environmental networks could support this application.

Keywords: Evapotranspiration, Sentinel satellites, Local weather stations, Two-Source Energy Balance, Irrigation management

Development and Implementation

Seasonality of Central European Forests – Results from Case Study 2

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This study investigates the seasonality of Central European forests by integrating multi-source datasets across three locations in Slovakia, Germany, and Austria. The research combines ground-based phenological observations with meteorological data, including in situ measurements, synoptic station records, and ERA5-Land reanalysis, to comprehensively assess the timing and duration of the forest growing season. Satellite-derived indices, including NDVI, EVI, and LAI, are also incorporated to provide spatially extensive perspectives on vegetation dynamics. The growing season is quantified using two complementary approaches. The first method calculates the growing season based on meteorological data employing the Normalised Daily Temperature Range (DTRT) seasonality index, which identifies seasonal transitions. The second method derives growing season parameters from satellite data, where one or multiple remote sensing products are used to estimate vegetation phenology. The integration of these methods enables a robust intercomparison that not only validates the seasonality index against satellite-derived metrics but also cross-checks both against direct ground observations. Our findings demonstrate a strong agreement among the three methodologies, with satellite-based estimations closely mirroring the growing season dynamics detected through meteorological data and ground observations. This consistency reinforces the reliability of combining diverse datasets to monitor forest phenology across heterogeneous landscapes. Moreover, the study highlights the potential of using integrated approaches to better understand how climatic variability influences forest ecosystems in Central Europe. By providing a detailed comparison of these methods across multiple locations, this research contributes valuable insights into the temporal dynamics of forest ecosystems. The outcomes have important implications for forest management, conservation planning, and the prediction of ecological responses to climate change, offering a comprehensive framework for future phenological studies in similar regions.

Keywords: Seasonality index, satellite, ERA5-Land reanalysis, vegetation index, forest, phenology

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Monitoring Thermal Variability in Urban Spaces: Assessing the Impact of Infrastructure on Urban Temperature Patterns

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In the discussion of uncomfortable thermal sensations in different parts of the city, people may experience varying conditions while walking outdoors. Thermal comfort differs when moving through blue, green, or grey infrastructure, especially during hot summer days.

Using Mobile Micrometeorological Carts (MMC) during the summer of 2022, measurements and monitoring were conducted on two separate occasions along two different routes. Data collection took place across various parts of Novi Sad, covering pedestrian routes. Monitoring of climatic parameters—including air temperature, humidity, globe temperature, wind speed, and solar radiation—was performed using MMC and Kestrel instruments at specific locations, four times a day during one-hour intervals (8:00, 11:00, 15:00, 19:30). The first route followed the pedestrian zone from Spens to the Danube River, while the second route extended from the Serbian National Theatre to Danube Park.

This type of micrometeorological monitoring allows for the identification of urban heat hotspots, predominantly associated with grey infrastructure. In contrast, blue (Danube) and green (parks) infrastructure demonstrated more favorable conditions, with temperatures several degrees lower than in fully paved areas. The rationale for stopping at multiple points throughout the routes was to gain a detailed understanding of temperature variations across different urban settings (or at the micro-scale). Such an approach can contribute to urban planning strategies aimed at improving infrastructure, mitigating the effects of excessive urbanization, and addressing climate change challenges that significantly impact the urban population.

The combination of movement and the complexity of urban morphology enhances the diversity of thermal conditions along a given route. This understanding opens possibilities for urban planning and design that prioritize environmental quality, where the thermal environment plays a crucial role in designing healthier and more liveable urban spaces.

Keywords: Thermal comfort, urban microclimate, mobile measurements, blue-green infrastructure

Monitoring of microclimatic parameters in Prague, Czechia: Critical assessment of research sites and evaluation of temperature measurements for 2023–2024

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There has been a growing interest in studying and monitoring urban climate in recent decades. In the 20th century, systematic observations using weather stations have been extended to observations and monitoring using purpose-built station networks located directly in urban areas. Here, researchers and promoters face several challenging tasks, e.g., ensuring the safety of the sensors while maintaining the representativeness of the measurement or facilitating accurate measurement with a limited budget for the sensors. In this work, we critically evaluated the network of 19 research locations, including 38 research points measuring air temperature, humidity, and, in some cases, wind velocity, global radiation, soil temperature, and soil moisture. We found that most of the locations were suitable for the study of urban and local climate; however, the representativeness of measurement for the assessment of the human thermal environment was limited or low in half of the research points. Focusing on air temperature, we found that the sensor and radiation shields used in Prague's urban network provided, in comparison with the official Czech Hydrometeorological Institute meteorological station, accurate daily mean temperature but overestimated the daily temperature amplitude. This further led to the overestimation of the values of summer climate indices. Regardless of the limitations mentioned above, we made several interesting findings based on the network measurements. The UHII was the highest at stations falling within local climate zones (LCZ) 8 and LCZ 2, followed by LCZ 5. Urban heat island intensity (UHII) increased at stations where the active surface was asphalt or pavement during heat waves. UHII was higher during heat waves at almost all urban stations during the nighttime period. For further measurements, several changes in the network were suggested.

Keywords: Urban climate monitoring, air temperature measurements, urban heat island intensity, local climate zones, microclimatic networks

Acknowledgment: The measurements was realized as a part of the project „Monitoring mikroklimatických parametrů urbanizovaného prostředí“ (č. PRK/40/01/003503/2018) of Operátor ICT a.s., Prague.

The impact of urban morphology on PM2.5 concentration under the LCZ scheme: A case study of Dhaka and Cardiff

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Urban morphology influences the spatial distribution of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) by directly affecting its sources and sinks and indirectly modifying the microclimate. While previous studies have examined these relationships using morphological metrics, many of these metrics prove challenging to apply in sustainable urban planning. In this study, we introduce an innovative approach by linking PM2.5 concentrations to the local climate zone (LCZ) classification.

We evaluated the impacts of urban morphology composition and configuration on PM2.5 by analysing differences both between LCZ categories (inter-category) and within built categories (intra-category), and by correlating PM2.5 concentrations with morphological metrics derived from the LCZ scheme. This analysis was conducted for two contrasting urban environments: Dhaka, a tropical megacity, and Cardiff, a cold temperate city. The contrasting climates and unique morphological patterns of these cities provide an ideal setting to investigate the influence of the built environment on air pollution concentrations.

Global Annual PM2.5 Grids from MODIS, 1998– for both cities were processed on a five-year basis from 2000 to 2024, and a time-series analysis was conducted to assess trends over the 24-year period. The data were subsequently compared with the LCZ maps of each city. Additionally, we performed a time-series analysis of meteorological data obtained from local weather stations for the same period and compared these findings with satellite imagery.

Our results indicate significant differences in PM2.5 concentrations both between LCZ categories and within built categories. The natural LCZ category consistently exhibited lower PM2.5 concentrations compared to built categories. Within built areas, higher concentrations were generally observed in more compact zones, with the hierarchy of high-rise > mid-rise > low-rise structures maintained throughout the year. This study offers a novel perspective on the relationship between morphology patterns and air quality, providing valuable scientific guidance for sustainable urban planning and air pollution mitigation strategies.

Keywords: PM2.5, LCZ scheme, morphology patterns, MODIS, Dhaka, Cardiff

Enhancing Public Health Preparedness: A Heat-Health Survey in Cairo, a Hot Desert Megacity

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Extreme heat poses a major public health risk in Cairo's hot-arid desert megacity, where urban heat island effects are intensifying hazards that climate change is expected to worsen. To enhance health preparedness, this study surveyed 550 Cairo pedestrians, evaluating heat exposure, thermal comfort, and health perceptions while accounting for socio-cultural factors.

The analysis revealed statistically significant correlations between thermal comfort perception (ASV) and environmental perceptions, including humidity (Spearman's rho, $\rho_s = 0.242$), wind speed ($\rho_s = -0.217$), solar radiation ($\rho_s = 0.390$), dust conditions (Spearman's rho, $\rho_s = 0.183$), and skin-wettedness ($\rho_s = 0.417$) perceptions. However, correlations between ASV and measured environmental conditions (air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation) were weak, highlighting subjective biases in environmental assessments and the need to consider socio-cultural factors in public health studies.

The study found a negative correlation ($\rho_s = -0.159$) between air-quality perception and ASV, suggesting that individuals who perceived higher temperatures also reported lower air quality. However, measured pollution levels (PM10, PM2.5, CO₂) showed no correlation with ASV, indicating a disconnect between perceived and actual air quality. No significant relationship was found between environmental parameters and general health satisfaction and quality of life, suggesting that thermal discomfort is not always linked to overall health perceptions.

Analysis revealed socio-cultural biases in self-reported health and environmental perceptions, especially regarding pollution and personal health. Individuals accustomed to high pollution may not acknowledge its impact, and their air quality perceptions were not location-dependent. A Pearson's Chi-squared test indicated that age, gender, and education significantly influenced ASV scores for thermal comfort. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions to reduce urban heat vulnerability and for integrating both subjective and objective environmental assessments into Cairo's urban planning and climate adaptation strategies.

Keywords: Heat-health survey, thermal comfort perception, socio-cultural factors, urban heat island, public health adaptation

Long Term Air Pollution Forecasting with PM10 and PM2.5 by Using Deep Learning-based Approach in city of Trabzon, Türkiye

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Air pollution is a critical environmental and public health issue, with significant implications for urban planning and policy-making. Accurate forecasting of air pollution levels is essential for effective pollution control measures and informed decision-making in environmental management. Additionally, researchers have focused to develop and improve emission inventories and calculate the emission rates of specific air pollutants in all over the world to be able to evaluate the relationship between air quality and climate change because the health risks of global air pollution intersect with the global climate change. In this study, we present a deep learning-based approach using Stacked Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to model and predict air pollution time series data in Trabzon, Türkiye. The proposed model is trained on historical air quality data, incorporating PM10 and PM2.5 concentration as the key pollutant. Unlike traditional statistical methods, Stacked LSTM networks effectively capture long-term dependencies and temporal patterns, improving predictive accuracy. In this study, a dataset consisting of daily PM10 and PM2.5 data from 5 Air Quality Monitoring Stations by T.R. Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change in Akçaabat, Beşirli, Fatih, Valilik and Meydan stations for the period of the last 20 years was used.

Our methodology involves preprocessing raw air pollution data, normalizing feature variables, and structuring the dataset into a supervised learning format. The model architecture consists of multiple LSTM layers stacked to enhance feature extraction and representation learning. We compare the performance of the Stacked LSTM model with conventional time-series prediction techniques, including ARMA and ARIMA, using evaluation metrics such as Pearson Correlation Coefficient and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

Keywords: Air pollution forecasting, deep learning, PM10 and PM2.5 prediction, stacked LSTM, time series analysis

The effect of urban morphology of Erzurum City on PM_{2.5} concentrations based on the Local Climate Zone (LCZ) classification

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Urban morphology plays a critical role in the distribution of air pollutants, including fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and ozone. The layout, design, and structure of cities can directly influence how pollutants are generated, dispersed, and concentrated within urban environments. Key factors which contribute to pollutant distribution are street configuration, building density, surface roughness, thermal properties, land use, height of buildings, and Urban Climate Zones (LCZ). City centers, with high population density, heavy traffic, industrial activities, and construction, are prime sources of PM_{2.5}. Reducing PM_{2.5} pollution is essential for enhancing urban air quality and overall public health. Urban morphology shapes PM_{2.5} distribution by influencing sources, sinks, and microclimates, but many existing metrics remain impractical for sustainable urban planning. Therefore, we propose a novel approach linking PM_{2.5} concentrations to the LCZ classification for Erzurum City, a cold temperate urban area characterized by significant PM_{2.5} pollution. We assessed the effects of urban morphology composition and configuration on PM_{2.5} by analysing the differences between LCZ categories (inter-category) and within built-up categories (intra-category). Additionally, we correlated PM_{2.5} concentrations with morphological metrics derived from the LCZ framework to further explore their relationship. The city's distinct cold climate and unique morphological features offer an ideal context for examining the relationship between the built environment and air pollution levels. To achieve this, global annual PM_{2.5} grids from MODIS, spanning 1998 to the present, were processed over a five-year period. A time-series analysis was then conducted to evaluate trends over the 24 years. In addition, a time-series analysis of meteorological data from local weather stations was performed for the same period, with the findings compared against satellite imagery. The PM_{2.5} concentrations from 2000 to 2020 in Erzurum are strongly correlated with the city's LCZ classifications. High-density urban and traffic zones (LCZ 1-10) serve as hotspots for PM_{2.5} pollution, whereas natural or sparsely built areas (LCZ A-G) exhibit lower concentrations. By aligning air quality management strategies with LCZ classifications, Erzurum can more effectively tackle its PM_{2.5} issues and enhance overall air quality. In addition, determining national legal limits for PM_{2.5} in the regulation is also gaining importance for air quality improvement efforts.

Keywords: Urban morphology, PM_{2.5}, Local Climate Zones, air quality management, satellite-based air pollution monitoring

Investigation of Precipitable Water Vapor and heavy rainfall relationship over Cyprus

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CyMETEO GNSS network installed in the framework of the strategic infrastructure project “Cyprus GNSS Meteorology Enhancement” (CYGMEN) aims at developing a GNSS-based PWV monitoring system, incorporated at the CyMETEO portal, that will be used for short-range weather forecasting and extreme weather events investigation over Cyprus. To perform the GNSS-based PWV product validation of CyMETEO, we created a complete dataset on heavy precipitation events over Cyprus for the 12 CyMETEO stations from 2020-2024, based on data from the Cyprus Department of Meteorology (CY DoM) and from the European Severe Weather Database (ESWD). Heavy precipitation days are considered the days with precipitation ≥ 20 mm. This is the criterion we chose to categorize a precipitation event as a day with heavy rain. From these cases, we selected certain extreme events with rain ≥ 40 mm, which were used to perform the validation of GNSS derived PWV and ZTD (Zenith Tropospheric Delay) employing radiosonde data from CY DoM. The GNSS tropospheric products (PWV, ZTD) were validated by utilizing existing independent datasets, such as ERA5 Reanalysis and IGRA Radiosonde data, during the selected extreme precipitation events. Additional extreme precipitation indices, as well as the relationship between PWV and precipitation during the selected extreme precipitation events over Cyprus during the period 2020-2024 were also investigated.

Keywords: precipitable water vapor, heavy rainfall, GNSS meteorology, Cyprus, extreme precipitation events

Acknowledgements: The present study is funded by project CYGMEN (Cyprus Gns Meteorology Enhancement, Ref. No. STRATEGIC INFRASTRUCTURES/1222/0198) which is co-funded by the Republic of Cyprus and the European Regional Development Fund, ERDF, in the frame of the operational programme «θαλασσια» 2021-2027 («European Partnerships» Programme ‘STRATEGIC INFRASTRUCTURES’ within the framework of the «RESTART 2016-2020» Programmes for Research, Technological Development and Innovation – Programmes for the Period May 2022 – March 2023).

PM2.5 Hotspots in a Megacity: Exploring the Impact of Urban Morphology in Cairo, Egypt Using LCZ Classification

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Urban morphology plays a significant role in shaping the spatial distribution of fine particulate matter (PM2.5) by directly influencing its sources and sinks, as well as indirectly altering microclimatic conditions. In this study, we propose a novel approach by correlating PM2.5 concentrations with the local climate zone (LCZ) classification, offering a more practical framework for understanding and addressing air quality challenges in urban environments.

We assessed the effects of urban morphology—both its composition and configuration—on PM2.5 levels by examining variations between different Local Climate Zone (LCZ) categories (inter-category) and within built-up LCZ categories (intra-category). This involved correlating PM2.5 concentrations with morphological metrics derived from the LCZ framework. The study focused on Cairo, Egypt, one of the world's megacities, whose contrasting climates and distinctive urban patterns provide an ideal setting to investigate how urban design, building density, and natural features influence air pollution levels.

Global Annual PM2.5 Grids derived from MODIS data, spanning from 1998 onward, were processed at five-year intervals from 2000 to 2024 for Cairo. A time-series analysis was conducted to evaluate trends in PM2.5 concentrations over the 24-year period. These data were then compared with Local Climate Zone (LCZ) maps for the city to explore the relationship between urban morphology and air quality.

The PM2.5 results from 2000 to 2020 in Cairo are closely tied to the city's LCZ categories. Dense urban and industrial zones are hotspots for PM2.5 pollution, while natural or sparsely built areas show lower concentrations. By aligning air quality interventions with LCZ classifications, Cairo can more effectively address its PM2.5 challenges and improve overall air quality. This study offers a novel perspective on the relationship between morphology patterns and air quality, providing valuable scientific guidance for sustainable urban planning and air pollution mitigation strategies.

Keywords: PM2.5, urban morphology, local climate zones, Cairo, air quality

Dissemination and Application

Start Them Young: Bridging Theory and Practice by Integrating GLOBE Protocols with Climate Education Tools in an Estonian School

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The complexity of climate change requires nurturing scientific curiosity and critical thinking from the earliest possible age. Early education in scientific thinking can shape lifelong critical understanding. We cannot wait for future generations to “save the world” and solve accumulated environmental challenges; instead, we must plant the seeds of ecological awareness and scientific reasoning in young minds before ingrained misconceptions take root. Teachers play a crucial role in this mission, yet they often lack the practical tools, methodologies and innovative approaches needed to effectively introduce climate science into their everyday teaching practices.

While theoretical frameworks and international protocols exist, their implementation in everyday teaching often remains complicated. We present a practical case study from a rural Estonian school where the "Climate Awareness" project's educational tools, initiated by the University of Tartu, were combined with GLOBE (Global Learning and Observations to Benefit the Environment) protocols to create a feasible framework for climate education. The study demonstrates how a small school established a system of meteorological observations and integrated them into the regular curriculum through cross-curricular activities.

The implemented system includes daily weather observations following GLOBE protocols, weekly data analysis integrated into mathematics classes, and longer thematic projects connecting meteorological data with various subjects, computer, math and language skills. Special attention was paid to ensuring that the system remains sustainable with minimal additional workload for teachers.

This educational framework aligns with the principles of the COST Action FAIRNESS, teaching students the importance of creating Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable scientific data. By following standardized GLOBE protocols, students learn not only about meteorological measurements but also about the significance of maintaining high-quality scientific data standards.

Keywords: GLOBE program, climate education, FAIR principles, meteorological observations, cross-curricular integration, rural education, practical implementation.

Microclimate monitoring in a sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) stand in Serbia

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Five Level II plots in Serbian forests are used to monitor parameters such as meteorology, deposition, and tree growth, employing standardized methods to explore cause-and-effect relationships within forest ecosystems. Meteorological factors influence the composition, structure, growth, health, and dynamics of these ecosystems. Collecting meteorological data at forest monitoring plots is crucial for understanding the impacts of climate change. To accurately interpret these effects, it's essential to assess the magnitude and temporal changes of meteorological variables, enabling their use as explanatory factors for other observations at the Level II plots in forests. Meteorological monitoring at these plots provides localized, in-forest information on key factors driving and influencing forest ecosystems. The data are vital for analysing air pollutant fluxes and deposition in forest stands, as well as understanding water and nutrient cycles, tree vitality, growth, phenology, and crown health. Since 2009, a comprehensive and harmonized meteorological time series for Serbia's intensive forest monitoring plots (Level II) has been available, with data accessible in the ICP Forests database. The dataset includes variables such as daily average air temperature (T_{mean} , in °C), daily minimum air temperature (T_{min} , in °C), daily maximum air temperature (T_{max} , in °C), and the daily sum of precipitation (P , in mm).

Monitoring over a long-term period can reveal trends. In this abstract, only the trend in the monthly average temperatures for July will be highlighted. In the past period, the mean monthly temperature in July for the sessile oak stand at the Level II plot increased, following the equation $y=0.0878x-155.05$, with a standard deviation described by the equation $y=-0.1261x+257.57$. Additionally, a decreasing trend in the coefficient of variation was observed, following the equation $y=-0.6918x+1409.4$ in this Level II plot. Based on this data, we observe a trend of rising average temperatures in sessile oak forests, which allows us to analyse this effect on growth, health, and dynamics of these oak forests.

Keywords: Microclimate monitoring, sessile oak, climate change, forest ecosystems

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Impact of selected Agri-PV Systems on microclimatic crop growing conditions and crop yield

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Various types of Agri-PV systems are currently being developed. PV modules not only use the incident radiation to generate power but also change the radiation field and microclimate of the micro-environment. PV modules partially shade the ground and break the wind, so that they directly and indirectly influence the growth conditions of plants under, between, and around the modules by changing microclimatic conditions. These changes are also dependent on the climate and weather. So far, however, only a few micrometeorological data sets of type- and site-specific systems are available to determine the growth conditions and their effects on crop-specific productivity. Therefore, the research questions are: What effects do PV module designs have on radiation-limited crop yield, and how are the microclimatic growing conditions for the crops and crop yield under the given site (soil, climate) and weather conditions affected?

In this context, a measurement campaign investigated an agricultural PV research facility at Schafflerhof (Marchfeld, Austria), located in a drought-prone area. Here, agricultural cultivation methods with a biological crop rotation between vertical rows of modules (bifacial panels) are applied. The approximately 3 m high modules are aligned in a north-south direction and have a row width of 10 m to enable cultivation with conventional agricultural machinery for crop production. In this system, microclimatic transect measurements with high temporal resolution were carried out, including photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), air and soil temperatures, air humidity, and soil water content. Results of the measurement campaign show the behavior of the variables along the transect. The results confirm the dominating effect of shading on the microclimatic conditions over the daily course, which resulted in the highest crop yields in the middle of the transect.

Further, a validation of the three-dimensional microclimatic model “ENVI-MET” was based on the measured data set. Simulated crop yields of selected crops under different APV system designs by calibrated crop models were presented. Considering different annual weather scenarios, winter wheat showed the lowest yield decline under shading compared to maize or soybean.

Keywords: Agri-PV systems, microclimate, crop yield, radiation, drought-prone areas

Urban Heat Extremes in Cairo, Egypt: Analyzing the 2022 Heatwave Event and its Environmental Impacts

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The July 2022 heatwave in Cairo was a prolonged and intense extreme weather event, significantly exceeding historical temperature thresholds. Analyzing ERA5-Land Reanalysis data, the study identified multiple heatwave phases, with 26 out of 31 days surpassing the 99th percentile of daily maximum temperature (36.07°C). The highest recorded temperature reached 39.45°C on July 28, with a 15-day uninterrupted heatwave from July 17 to the end of the month. This extreme heat event was influenced by both global and local factors, including climate change-driven temperature rise, urban heat island effects, and atmospheric high-pressure systems. Air quality data from Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI and MERRA-2 revealed significant atmospheric changes during the heatwave, including increased Absorbing Aerosol Index (AAI) and elevated surface ozone (O₃) levels. These variations suggest enhanced dust transport, biomass burning, and intensified photochemical activity, contributing to poor air quality and increased health risks. The study underscores the urgent need for integrated climate adaptation strategies, improved air quality management, and continuous monitoring to mitigate the environmental and societal impacts of extreme heat events in urban settings like Cairo.

Keywords: Heatwave, Cairo, ERA-5, Air Pollution, AAI, Ozone, Urban

The influence of spring and summer air temperatures and rainfall on the growth of European beech trees (*Fagus sylvatica*) in Lopare

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Climate change has a profound and long-term and large impact on the growth and dynamic of forests. In this paper, the influence of mean monthly air temperatures and precipitation in the spring (March, April, May- MAM) and summer (June, July, August- JJA) months on the width of the European beech trees (*Fagus sylvatica*) at the lower limit of the altitudinal distribution of beech forests, within the belt transitioning to oak forests, was analysed. Data on climatic elements were taken from the network E-OBS database and cover the period from 1950 to 2023, and data on the width of the years were obtained based on field research, by sampling cores from dominant beech trees. Statistical methods, including correlation and regression analyses, were used to identify the key factors that influence the growth of beech trees. The results show that air temperatures and precipitation in the spring and summer months are significantly related to the growth of beech trees, while dry years and extremely high temperatures had a strong negative impact. This analysis contributes to a better understanding of the response and adaptation of forest ecosystems to changes in climatic elements and can serve as a basis for developing future forest management and adaptation strategies.

Keywords: European beech, temperatures, precipitation, tree-ring width

Determination of CO₂ fluxes of canola plant using Eddy Covariance micrometeorological method

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With the protocols made between countries regarding climate change, it is aimed to reduce global greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) and increase the amount of sinks. Agriculture is one of the components taken into account in the global GHG budgets. The important point here is to determine the emission and sink coefficients specific to the countries' own plants. If these coefficients are not available, the calculation approaches recommended by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) need to be used. This situation constitutes a significant obstacle in determining the national GHG budgets of the countries accurately. The first step in studies on this subject is to determine the net ecosystem (NEE) change and its components through measurements. In this study, it is aimed to determine GHG gas (CO₂) exchanges between the plant surface and the atmosphere by the Eddy Covariance (EC) method which is one of the micrometeorological methods. The research study was carried out in the field of Atatürk Soil, Water and Agricultural Meteorology Research Institute in Kırklareli province, Türkiye. In this context, data were collected and analyzed throughout the plant growing period with the EC and agricultural meteorological stations. Within the scope of the study, the growing period of canola (*Brassica napus Oleifera* sp.), known as an important oil plant worldwide, between October 2015 and June 2016 was investigated. As a result; the times when the negative values of NEE were the highest (the plant absorbs CO₂ into its body) occurred during the leaf development, flowering and seed formation periods of the plant. In other phenological periods, the amount of CO₂ emission was higher than the amount removed. During the growing period, the plant removed approximately 116.3 g of carbon from the atmosphere per m² and the average of daily NEE values was calculated as -0.47 g C m⁻².

Keywords: CO₂ flux, Eddy Covariance method, net ecosystem exchange, canola

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An Investigation on UHI of Erzurum City by Evaluating Micrometeorological Measurements and Global SUHI

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The urban heat island (UHI) effect describes the temperature difference between urban areas and their surrounding environments, a consequence of urbanization that has been studied for over a century. There are two main types of UHI: canopy UHI, which is based on air temperature differences, and surface UHI, derived from land surface temperature comparisons facilitated by satellite data. While their intensities are similar annually, they exhibit different variations over time. Urbanization alters the surface energy budget through changes in albedo, evaporation, heat storage in structures, and thermal dissipation, with factors such as pollution, city size, and synoptic conditions further influencing UHI intensity. Despite extensive research across numerous cities, robustness in studies has been inconsistent, often due to variations in methodological approaches, weather controls, and definitions of urban versus rural measurement sites (Chakraborty and Lee, 2019). While large mega-cities have been the primary focus of UHI research, smaller urban areas have received less attention in the existing literature. Additionally, the temporal and seasonal variability of UHI intensity remains insufficiently explored on a global scale. This study aims to address these gaps by analyzing and comparing the UHI effect in Erzurum City, Turkey and Cardiff City, UK over a 17-year period (2003-2020). The research will utilize data from two meteorological stations: one in the city center and another at an airport station located in a rural area. Key meteorological variables, including maximum and minimum temperatures (Tmax and Tmin), rainfall, sunshine, and air frost days, will be used to assess UHI intensity. To enhance the analysis, UHI results will be compared with data from the Global Surface UHI (SHUI) Explorer, an interactive tool built on the Google Earth Engine platform. The SHUI Explorer integrates MODIS TERRA and AQUA Land Surface Temperature (LST) data, providing a standardized and practical method for monitoring UHI intensities across different urban areas. By comparing these findings with global UHI patterns, the research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of UHI dynamics and provide valuable insights into the temporal and spatial variability of UHI in smaller urban settings.

Keywords: Urban heat island, micrometeorological measurements, surface temperature, Erzurum, Suhi Explorer

Acknowledgment: The meteorological measurements were provided by the Turkish State Meteorological Service at Erzurum Local Meteorological Stations.

Heavy rain intensity data application used at the local scale

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Rain intensity is one of the decisive environmental parameters influencing many human activities within a certain area, including agriculture and further plant production. Further to that, it remains a limiting factor for many activities in the construction and risk management concerning floods, mainly flash floods. Statistical evaluation is done over the time series of rain data measured at short time intervals. The data are derived either from analogue records of pluviometers or from digital data of tipping bucket rain gauges or weighing rain gauges. In our case we used 27 year time series of combined one minute data from pluviometers with floating chambers (data manually digitized from 1995-2009 period) and one minute data from weighing rain gauges with digital outputs from 2005-2021 data series. 5 years parallel records from both classic pluviometer and weighing rain gauge at a few stations enabled the comparison of these data series. No statistically significant differences in trends were found. Moving window statistics when setting 14 time windows from 5 min. to 1440 min was applied to calculate the statistical occurrence of the particular rain intensity within 9 periodicities from 2 to 200 years. This statistics was applied to data from 72 meteorological stations in Slovakia, which enabled to create spatial distribution of each time interval for each period and gridded datasets for grids of 0,5 x 0,5 km. The local application is concentrated in the evaluation of the micro-basins flash floods by modelling the water flow at the spatial level of a few square kilometers based on the respective grided data. Terrain parameters, ground cover including the known artificial breaks and constructions and soil characteristics were considered to model the water level in the particular point of the selected micro-basin. The system is freely available on the internet.

Keywords: Heavy rain, flash floods, gridded datasets, freely available alert system

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Beyond FAIRNESS Strategies

Beyond FAIRNESS: Strategic Pathways for Global Synergies and Sustainable Data Practices

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The FAIRNESS initiative has advanced the adoption of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data principles in micrometeorological and environmental networks. As these practices evolve, there is a need to explore strategies that go beyond FAIR standards to ensure long-term impact, sustainability, and global collaboration.

This presentation will outline key strategies to extend the FAIRNESS framework, starting with global harmonisation efforts aimed at aligning FAIR principles with international initiatives such as GEO and Copernicus. By fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, we can address shared challenges in data interoperability across climate science, hydrology, and related fields, creating unified frameworks that maximise the value of environmental data.

Policy and governance also play a crucial role in driving FAIRNESS beyond its current scope. Embedding FAIR principles into funding criteria and regulatory standards can ensure long-term sustainability and widespread adoption. Citizen science and open-access platforms represent additional pathways for engaging the public in environmental monitoring, increasing transparency and societal impact.

The following strategies will be explored: (i) Global Harmonisation Efforts- Advocate for the alignment of FAIR principles across international environmental monitoring networks; (ii) AI and Data Automation- Integrate AI/ML to enhance data interoperability, automate quality assurance, and streamline analysis processes; (iii) Interdisciplinary Synergies- Foster collaboration across disciplines to develop shared frameworks and maximise the impact of FAIR data; (iv) Education and Capacity Building- Establish training programmes and integrate FAIR practices into academic and professional curricula; (v) Policy Integration- Encourage policymakers to incorporate FAIR data principles into funding, regulations, and long-term sustainability initiatives; (vi) Citizen Science and Open Access- Promote FAIR data use in citizen science projects and public-access platforms to enhance societal engagement; (vii) Climate Resilience Applications- Utilise FAIR data strategies to address environmental sustainability and climate adaptation challenges.

This presentation aims to inspire dialogue on expanding FAIRNESS strategies, fostering innovation, and building a truly global network of sustainable environmental data practices.

Keywords: FAIR data principles, global harmonisation, data interoperability, AI in environmental data, policy integration, climate resilience, capacity building

The role of entrepreneurship and innovation in advancing and sustaining FAIR micrometeorological research

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The sustainability of micrometeorological research remains a critical challenge, particularly when scientific funding expires, often leaving valuable data and infrastructure at risk. This issue is especially significant in the context of FAIR (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable*) data, where the discontinuation of services such as micrometeorological networks and data hosting web platforms could render previously FAIR data inaccessible - effectively undermining its long-term utility. While traditional scientific projects are essential, they are frequently constrained by administrative barriers and funding, limiting the translation of research outputs into practical solutions.

The role of entrepreneurship and innovation in advancing and sustaining scientific work in micrometeorology is gaining increasing significance, especially in the context of climate adaptation. This work explores how entrepreneurial strategies can bridge the gap between micrometeorological research and practical applications, offering pathways to ensure the sustainability, scalability, and continued “FAIRNESS” of scientific research.

Through the presentation of successful case studies and current initiatives, key strategies are outlined to support meteorologists in transforming research into impactful products and services that maintain accessibility and usability over time. A central example includes insights from my start-up project, *Urban Heat Adapt*, which delivers micrometeorological data as a service to climate adaptation managers and urban planners in Germany. This case study illustrates how entrepreneurial initiatives can transform meteorological research into actionable tools for decision-makers to strengthen urban resilience to climate risks.

The discussion highlights the importance of fostering collaboration between researchers and private sector actors, advocating for structured frameworks that connect scientists with entrepreneurs to maximise the societal impact of meteorological research. This contribution offers practical recommendations for building resilient micrometeorological infrastructure, and underscores how entrepreneurial approaches can serve as catalysts for innovation, societal benefit, and the preservation of FAIR micrometeorological data.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, FAIR data, innovation, start-up project

Construction of a Climate Dataset for Long-Term Forest Site Investigations in Central Slovakia

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Long-term meteorological measurements and quality-controlled climate datasets are of fundamental importance for forest management planning, tree growth studies, and site analysis. These constructed datasets include: i) historical meteorological station measurements, ii) various gridded reanalysis datasets, iii) decades of forestry meteorological measurements, and iv) bias-corrected climate model projections for the future.

Integrating multiple data sources provides an opportunity to analyse climate conditions over nearly a quarter of a millennium, from the second half of the 19th century to the end of the 21st century. Our investigations were carried out in the Banska Bystrica District in central Slovakia. Data from four meteorological stations (Banská Bystrica, Banská Štiavnica, Dobroč and Pohorelá) and their closest grid points were processed.

Monthly meteorological data (pressure, temperature, humidity, precipitation, wind speed, and direction) for Slovakia were recorded in yearbooks dating back to the second half of the 19th century. In this study, historical climate data for Slovakia were obtained from the yearbooks of the Royal Hungarian Central Institute of Meteorology and Earth Magnetism (RHCIMEM) for the period 1871–1918. By 1871, meteorological measurements were already being conducted at 22 stations, with observations taken at least three times a day. This number increased to 162 stations by 1900. Monthly data series for the four selected stations were compiled and homogenized.

Additionally, we utilized the CRU gridded dataset starting from 1900 and the FORESEE (Open Database FOR ClimatE Change-Related Impact Studies in CEntral Europe) database, which covers the period from 1951 to 2100 at a 0.1-degree resolution. These data were linked to local forest meteorological measurements and the ERA5 reanalysis dataset. Our primary focus is on precipitation and temperature time series, with additional analyses of extreme weather events. After presenting the unified database, we analyse differences between overlapping data series and discuss key findings from forestry studies.

Keywords: Long-term, quality-controlled, meteorological data, gridded dataset, extreme weather events

Temporal trends in temperature-related mortality in the eastern Mediterranean region: Evidence for maladaptation to heat and cold

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The eastern Mediterranean region is experiencing rising temperature trends that exceed global averages, making it a climate change hotspot. While previous studies have extensively examined the effects of extreme heat and cold on human mortality and morbidity under both current and future climate scenarios, no research has explored temporal trends in temperature-related mortality or historical adaptation to heat and cold extremes in this region. This study focuses on cardiovascular mortality and analyses the temporal evolution of Minimum Mortality Temperature (MMT) and the disease-specific cold- and heat-attributable mortality fractions in three representative eastern Mediterranean locations: Athens, Thessaloniki, and Cyprus. Data on daily cardiovascular mortality (ICD-10 code: I00–I99) and meteorological parameters were available from 1999–2019 for Athens, 1999–2018 for Thessaloniki, and 2004–2019 for Cyprus. Cardiovascular MMT and mortality fractions were estimated using time-series Poisson regressions with distributed lag nonlinear models (DLNM), adjusting for seasonal and long-term trends through rolling sub-period analyses at each site. The findings show that in Athens, MMT declined from 23°C (67.5th percentile) in 1999–2007 to 21.8°C (62nd percentile) in 2011–2019, while in Cyprus, it fell from 26.3°C (79th percentile) in 2004–2012 to 23.9°C (66.5th percentile) in 2011–2019. In Thessaloniki, the decrease in MMT was minimal. Across all studied regions, the proportion of mortality attributed to both cold and heat increased over time. In conclusion, the rising fraction of mortality linked to cold and the declining trend in MMT suggest maladaptation to extreme temperatures in warm climates, underscoring the need for targeted public health policies and interventions.

Keywords: Temperature-related mortality, Mediterranean, climate scenarios, cold, public health policies

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